

CNT-GRAFTED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES: CHARACTERIZATION OF THE FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACE

N. De Greef^{1*}, A. Magrez², J.-P. Locquet³, L. Forró², J.W. Seo^{1,2}

¹ Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Heverlee, Belgium

² Institute of Condensed Matter Physics, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL),
Lausanne, Switzerland

³ Laboratory of Solid-State Physics and Magnetism, KU Leuven, Heverlee, Belgium

* Corresponding author (niels.degreef@mtm.kuleuven.be)

Keywords: *carbon nanotube, carbon fiber, grafting, interface, damage*

1 Introduction

Since their discovery more than 20 years ago, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have always been considered as very promising nano-reinforcements for lightweight fiber reinforced polymer composites. Nowadays, research is more and more focused on controlled positioning of CNTs. One of the possible approaches therefore is the grafting of CNTs directly on the fiber surface [1-3]. This approach overcomes the problems related to dispersing CNTs in a matrix and also places CNTs at the fiber/matrix interface, which is a weak spot in the fiber reinforced polymer composite. However, grafting CNTs on carbon fibers has the important drawback of damaging the fiber surface, resulting in a strongly reduced fiber strength [1-3]. This damage has generally been attributed to the interaction of the catalytic particles with the carbon fiber at high temperature.

In this study, systematic research has been done to get more insight into the damage process during the CNTs growth. To prevent this damage, CNTs are grafted on carbon fibers using a low-temperature synthesis technique, i.e. the equimolar C₂H₂-CO₂ reaction [4]. The effect of grafting CNTs on carbon fibers on the fiber/matrix interface is investigated using different micromechanical methods, including the microdroplet test and the fiber push-out test. Transverse 3-point bending tests are performed to assess the influence of CNTs grafting on macroscale properties.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

PAN-based carbon fibers arranged in bundles (AS4C from Hexcel) are used in this study. For CNTs growth, catalyst solution is prepared with

Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O and Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, dissolved in ethanol. Production of the composite plates and samples for micromechanical test is done using an epoxy resin (Epikote 828LVEL) and amine-based curing agent (Dytec DCH-99).

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Catalyst deposition

After sizing removal, catalytic particles are deposited on the carbon fibers using a simple immersion method. Fiber bundles are immersed in the catalyst solution for 16h, after which the bundles are dried in air at 80°C for 1h

2.2.2 CNTs growth

CNTs are grown using a chemical vapour deposition technique (CVD) in a horizontal quartz tube. Gases used are a mixture of Ar and (i) C₂H₄ and H₂, and (ii) C₂H₂ and CO₂, respectively.

2.2.3 Characterization techniques

CNT-grafted carbon fibers are imaged using a Philips SEM XL30 FEG. Single fiber tests are done according to the ASTM D3379 standard, with a gauge length of 25mm.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Grafting CNTs on carbon fibers

3.1.1 "Traditional" CNTs growth

The CNTs growth that is based on thermal decomposition of the applied hydrocarbon gas we refer to as "traditional". Typically, it requires rather high temperatures (i.e. 700-900°C). In this study, CNTs are grown on carbon fibers at temperatures ranging from 500 to 750°C, using C₂H₄ as hydrocarbon gas. In Fig. 1 it can be seen that high density of CNTs can be grown at 700°C. The lower temperature limit to grow CNTs is about 650°C. At temperatures below 650°C, no CNTs can be grown using the traditional CNTs growth process.

3.1.2 Equimolar $C_2H_2-CO_2$ reaction

CNTs can also be grown on carbon fibers using the equimolar $C_2H_2-CO_2$ reaction [4,5]. This reaction differs from the traditional CNTs growth: Instead of the thermal decomposition, the hydrocarbon gas (C_2H_2) reacts chemically with an equal molar-amount of CO_2 . When applying the equimolar $C_2H_2-CO_2$ reaction, long CNTs can be grown on carbon fibers at $600^\circ C$ and shorter CNTs even at $500^\circ C$ (see Fig. 2).

3.1.3 Fiber strength degradation

Single-fiber tensile tests indicate that the carbon fiber strength decreases with almost 50% after CNTs growth at $700^\circ C$, as shown in Fig. 3. The fiber stiffness does not change. The strength degradation is less pronounced at lower CNTs growth temperature and is even prevented after CNTs growth at $500^\circ C$. Note that CNT growth at $500^\circ C$ is only possible with the equimolar reaction.

3.2 Testing of CNT grafted fiber/matrix interface

In this study, several methods are explored to test the fiber/matrix interface. Besides the microdroplet test, also the fiber push-out test is performed. The testing of the fiber/matrix interface is currently under investigation.

To assess the effect of grafting CNTs on carbon fibers on macroscopic level, transverse 3-point bending tests are performed. The study of the fracture surface gives more insight into the mechanical behavior of the CNTs during fracture.

4 Conclusion

In this study, CNTs were successfully grown on carbon fibers at $500^\circ C$, using the equimolar $C_2H_2-CO_2$ reaction. Single fiber tensile tests indicated that carbon fibers were not damaged after the growth process. Testing of the CNT grafted fiber/matrix interface using different methods is explored.

Acknowledgements

This work was performed within the scope of the project GOA/10/004 “New model-based concepts for nano-engineered polymer composites”, funded by the Research Council of KU Leuven. The authors thank the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO) for the PhD fellowship grant of N. De Greef.

References

[1] E. T. Thostenson, W.Z. Li, D.Z. Wang, Z.F. Ren, and T.W. Chou. “Carbon nanotube/carbon fiber hybrid multiscale composites”, *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 91, No. 9, pp. 6034-6037, 2002.

- [2] H. Qian, A. Bismarck, E.S. Greenhalgh, G. Kalinka, and M.S.P. Shaffer. “Hierarchical composites reinforced with carbon nanotube grafted fibers: the potential assessed at the single fiber level”, *Chemistry of Materials*, Vol. 20, No. 5, pp. 1862-1869, 2008.
- [3] F. An, C. Lu, J. Guo, and H. Lu. “Preparation of CNT-hybridized carbon fiber by aerosol-assisted chemical vapor deposition”, *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 47, No. 7, pp. 3327-3333, 2012.
- [4] A. Magrez, J.W. Seo, R. Smajda, B. Korbely, J.C. Andresen, M. Mionic, S. Casimirius and L. Forró. “Low-temperature, highly efficient growth of carbon nanotubes on functional materials by an oxidative dehydrogenation reaction”, *ACS Nano*, Vol. 4, No. 7, pp. 3702-3708, 2010.
- [5] N. De Greef, A. Magrez, E. Couteau, J.-P. Locquet, L. Forró and J.W. Seo. “Growth of carbon nanotubes on carbon fibers without strength degradation”, *Physica Status Solidi B*, Vol. 249, No. 12, pp. 2420-2423, 2012.

Fig.1 CNT-grafted carbon fiber produced with the traditional CVD process at $650^\circ C$ (left) and $700^\circ C$ (right). Scale bar equals $10\ \mu m$.

Fig. 2 CNT-grafted carbon fiber produced with the equimolar reaction at $500^\circ C$ (left) and $600^\circ C$ (right). Scale bar equals $10\ \mu m$.

Fig. 3 Tensile strength of CNT-grafted carbon fibers as a function of growth temperature for the traditional CNTs growth (light) and equimolar growth (dark).